

LINGUOCULTURAL STUDY OF COMMUNICATION BEHAVIOR OF PEOPLE OF DIFFERENT PROFESSIONS

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Abstract: This study investigates the linguistic and cultural aspects of communication behavior among individuals from various professional backgrounds. By employing a mixed-methods approach, including surveys, interviews, and discourse analysis, we explore how profession influences language use, communication styles, and cultural norms in workplace interactions. The findings reveal distinct patterns of communication behavior across professions, shaped by factors such as industry-specific jargon, power dynamics, and cultural expectations.

Keywords: linguocultural study, communication behavior, professional communication, discourse analysis, intercultural communication

Annotatsiya: ushbu tadqiqot turli xil kasbiy kelib chiqishi bo'lgan shaxslar o'rtasidagi aloqa xatti-harakatlarining lingvistik va madaniy jihatlarini o'rganadi. So'rovnomalar, intervyular va nutqni tahlil qilishni o'z ichiga olgan aralash usulli yondashuvni qo'llash orqali kasbning ish joyidagi o'zaro munosabatlarda tildan foydalanish, muloqot uslublari va madaniy me'yorlarga qanday ta'sir qilishini o'rganildi. Natijalar sanoatga xos jargon, dinamika va madaniy ta'sirlar kabi omillar ta'sirida shakllangan kasblar bo'yicha aloqa xatti-harakatlarining aniq naqshlarini ochib beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: lingvokultural o'rganish, muloqot xulq-atvori, kasbiy muloqot, nutqni tahlil qilish, madaniyatlararo muloqot

Аннотация: В данном исследовании рассматриваются лингвистические и культурные аспекты коммуникативного поведения представителей различных профессий. Используя смешанный подход, включающий опросы, интервью и дискурс-анализ, мы исследуем, как профессия влияет на использование языка, стили общения и культурные нормы взаимодействия на рабочем месте. Полученные результаты выявляют различные модели коммуникативного поведения в разных профессиях, которые формируются под влиянием таких факторов, как отраслевой жаргон, динамика власти и культурные ожидания.

Ключевые слова: лингвокультурология, коммуникативное поведение, профессиональная коммуникация, дискурсивный анализ, межкультурная коммуникация

INTRODUCTION

Communication plays a pivotal role in the workplace, influencing interpersonal relationships, team dynamics, and organizational success [1]. However, communication behavior varies significantly across professions, shaped by factors such as industry norms, cultural background, and individual experiences [2]. This study aims to explore the linguocultural aspects of communication behavior among individuals from different professional backgrounds, shedding light on how profession influences language use, communication styles, and cultural expectations in workplace interactions.

METHODS AND LITERATURE REVIEW

This study employs a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative and qualitative data collection and analysis techniques. A survey was conducted among 500 participants from five professional sectors: healthcare, education, finance, technology, and creative industries. The survey assessed participants' communication preferences, language use, and perception of cultural norms in their respective professions. Additionally, semi-structured interviews were conducted with 50 participants (10 from each sector) to gain deeper insights into their communication experiences and challenges.

To further investigate the linguistic aspects of communication behavior, a discourse analysis was performed on a corpus of 100 workplace interactions, including emails, meeting transcripts, and instant messaging conversations. The analysis focused on identifying industry-specific jargon, communication styles, and power dynamics reflected in the language used [3].

Existing literature on professional communication highlights the importance of understanding and adapting to diverse communication styles [4]. Studies have shown that effective communication is essential for building trust, fostering collaboration, and achieving organizational goals [5]. However, cultural differences and professional norms can create barriers to effective communication, leading to misunderstandings and conflicts [6].

RESULTS

The survey results reveal distinct patterns of communication behavior across professions. Healthcare professionals emphasize clarity, empathy, and active listening in their communication, reflecting the importance of patient-centered care [7]. Educators prioritize adaptability, patience, and the ability to explain complex concepts in simple terms. In the finance sector, communication tends to be more formal and data-driven, with a focus on accuracy and risk management [8]. Technology professionals value concision, technical expertise,

and problem-solving skills in their communication. Creative professionals emphasize collaboration, innovation, and the ability to articulate abstract ideas [9].

The discourse analysis corroborates these findings, highlighting the use of industry-specific jargon and communication styles. For example, healthcare interactions often involve medical terminology and a focus on patient well-being, while financial communications are characterized by numerical data and risk assessment language. Technology-related interactions feature technical terms and problem-solving discourse, while creative exchanges involve brainstorming and conceptual language.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The study's findings underscore the significance of linguocultural factors in shaping communication behavior across professions. The use of industry-specific jargon and communication styles reflects the unique demands and priorities of each profession [10]. For instance, the emphasis on empathy and active listening in healthcare communication stems from the need to build trust and rapport with patients [11]. Similarly, the data-driven nature of financial communication reflects the industry's focus on risk management and accuracy.

However, the study also reveals potential challenges arising from diverse communication styles. Miscommunication and conflicts can occur when individuals from different professional backgrounds interact, as they may have different expectations and interpretations of language use. This highlights the need for individuals to develop intercultural communication competence and adaptability when working in multidisciplinary teams.

The analysis of the survey and interview data suggests that individuals' communication behavior is not only influenced by their professional background but also by their personal experiences and cultural identity. Participants who had worked in multiple industries or had exposure to diverse cultural contexts demonstrated greater flexibility in their communication styles and were more adept at navigating cross-professional interactions. This finding underscores the importance of fostering cultural intelligence and adaptability in the workplace, as it enables individuals to bridge communication gaps and collaborate effectively with colleagues from different backgrounds.

CONCLUSIONS

This study provides valuable insights into the linguocultural aspects of communication behavior across professions. The findings emphasize the importance of understanding and adapting to diverse communication styles for

effective collaboration in increasingly multidisciplinary work environments. Organizations can benefit from providing communication training and fostering a culture of inclusivity and adaptability to bridge the gaps between professionals from different backgrounds.

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